

The Recall and Communicative Effectiveness of Computer Generated Imagery in Television Advertisements

A Case Study of Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract: In the global advertising industry, and more specifically in Lagos state today, Computer Generated Imagery (CGI) has over time influenced the development and production quality of television contents, including product advertising. However, little or no research has been conducted on how CGI can be effective to television advertisements. Adopting a slightly modified form of the AIDA model of measuring advertising effectiveness, a sample size of 398 respondents was taken in Lagos Nigeria with valid responses of 362 participants. Following two hypotheses testing, the study showed a significant relationship between CGI and recall/ communicative effectiveness of television advertisements respectively. Also, the study revealed that CGI-embedded TV adverts are perceived to be more effective over non-CGI-embedded adverts with respect to attention, interest/desire and action for recall-inducing and effective product communication.

Keywords: Communication, Computer Generated Imagery (CGI), Television advertisements, AIDA model.

1. INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly competitive global market such as we have today, the need for effective advertising campaigns is of great importance. The market has become increasingly flooded with varieties of similar products and services with the consumer left with many attractive alternatives from which he or she may choose to satisfy his or her varying needs or wants. Consequently, this market situation has given rise to the product manufacturers' and service providers' need for improved marketing strategies as well as the production of more effective, specific-target-oriented, television advertisement with increasingly far greater reach, memory-stimulating and interest-arresting qualities in an effective bid to brand their individual products or services as 'the consumer's ultimate choice' in the hearts of the target population. This imperative advertising agenda has, over the years, engineered the common interest of most advertising people in Computer Generated Imagery.

The application of computer graphics to create images in art, video games, films, television programs and advertisement, known as Computer Generated Imagery (CGI), has contributed immensely to the quality of production output in the television advertising industry. Salomon (1994) suggested that television advertising encompasses almost all, if not all, the attributes that other forms of advertisements possess as it involves colour, music, texts and vivid images which, more often than not, defines the distinguishing attributes of the various forms of advertising media. In his seminal work on media and cognition, Salomon argued that every technological medium "entails some particular, even unique, attributes that matter or can be made to matter in learning" or processing of information (Salomon, 1994). In television advertising, one of such attributes is 'Sensory Stimulation' which often stimulates (emotional) arousal; which, in turn, influences the decision and actions of the audience or consumers. In an expansive stretch of literature, researchers have connected heightened arousal, which is one of the key constructs in the study of human emotion and motivation, with CGI attributes such as colour, music, motion and vivid images (Farley & Grant, 1976; Seidman, 1981; Detenber & Simons, 1998; Biocca, 2002). In fact, or appeals containing high levels of sensory stimulation are generally associated with high levels of audience arousal (Grabe, 2000). From this research, one could surmise that computer-generated imagery, which stimulates the visual and auditory senses, should augment audiences' arousal levels and, hence, influence their end choices, preferences or consumption behavior.

Research indicates that arousal influences how individuals encode and store messages. Specifically, individuals pay more attention to arousing messages, and they also recall such messages better (Grabe, 2000). This is most profitable in advertising as the effectiveness of adverts can be measured via the measure of its content that the audience is able to, not just absorb but also, remember. Weiner (1990, 1992), in his arousal theory, posits a positive link between arousal and learning. In more specific terms, emotionally arousing advertisements can be said to enhance audience motivation and subsequent preferential behaviour. Thus, the potentials of CGI to do such things as arousing emotions and influencing cognition could support the claim that adding CGI to television advertisements has led or would lead to a more interested, loyal and more motivated audience. Hence, its impact on television advertisement was assessed in terms of its attention-arresting, interest/desire –arousing and end-action-inspiring potentials, strictly from the perspective of consumers, as it rubs on message-clarity and how much of advert contents the consumer is able to remember.

2. TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT AND AUDIENCE BEHAVIOUR

Audience, in this discuss, are the part of the population who are exposed to television adverts produced and aired, while the consumers are the specific end users of the advertised products and or services.

Audience behaviour is the way the audience act or react when television-adverts air. Various studies conducted between 1962 and 2015 indicate that a substantial proportion of television programme audiences do not watch advertisements. Using several techniques, researchers have attempted to estimate the extent to which television audiences actually watch or avoid advertisements. Nuttall (1962) investigated this with day-after recall. Allen (1965) used time-lapse cameras to photograph the behaviour of television audiences in selected households. Steiner (1966) enlisted students as "observers" within the selected households to observe the behaviour of other members. Wolfe, Brown, Thompson, and Greenberg (1966) used a combination of post-exposure interviews and in-home observers. Twyman (1969) used both diaries and telephone interviews which coincided with advert breaks. Bunn (1982) used the increase in electricity consumption during breaks to estimate the extent to which audiences did other things than view television at these times. Collett (1986) developed a combination of video camera and recorder named "C-box". Brennan and Syn (2001) used time spent with "eyes on screen". All these studies agree in findings that a substantial proportion of programme audiences do not watch advertisements. Besides, technological innovations such as V-chip and Digital Video Recorders, which are devices that allow users to both view and store television programs without adverts, are in no wise helping the advertising industry.

According to Don and Nevan (1993), the size of audience for advertisements shown on television is a matter of vital concern to advertisers. There is no use spending huge amounts of money both to produce and air television adverts if no one is paying attention to them. In the opinion of Mackenzie, Lutz and Belch (1986), qualitative factors associated with the content and or execution of an advert influences its eventual effectiveness. This has given rise to the need to investigate the impact of such factors such as CGI, a major qualitative factor associated with the content and production of adverts, on television advertisements.

2.1. Information-Processing Styles and Consumer Behaviour

To create effective and arousing adverts, we need to understand the diversity of ways the audience, to whom such advertising stimuli are targeted, process the information/messages passed across to them. Proctor and Stone (1982) noted that the principal aim of consumer behaviour analysis is to explain why consumers act in particular ways under certain circumstances. It tries to determine the factors that influence consumer behaviour, especially in terms of their preferences in consumption/purchase.

Bitner (1992) posits that responses (to television adverts) can be cognitive, affective or both at the same time which often leads to certain behavioural responses that may be favourable or unfavourable towards the achievement of the objectives of producing and placing the advert in the first place, be it CGI-embedded or not. Researchers have long been intrigued by these two individual characteristics, affect and cognition, which have an influence on advertising effectiveness (Harris and Moore, 1990; Fabrigar and Petty, 1999; Zhang and Buda, 1999).

According to Cacciopo and Petty (1982), some individuals may exhibit a tendency to engage in and enjoy thinking when exposed to an advert; the advert gets them thinking. The cognitive element of attitude, as posited by Baumgartner and Laghi, (2012), concerns perceptions, concepts, and

beliefs regarding the attitude object which in this case are television adverts as well as the advertised products or services. It dwells on what an advert causes the audience to think.

Some individuals, when exposed to an emotionally charged advertising appeal, may exhibit a characteristic tendency to experience their emotions with greater magnitude of intensity (Aaker, Stayman, Hagerty, 1986). The affective component includes feelings toward the attitude object (Baumgartner et al, 2012). It borders on how television adverts make the audience feel (i.e. the emotions it arouses) and, consequently, the subsequent behaviour it triggers. According to Sørensen (2008), emotions and feelings play an important role in our everyday life and the way we make decisions.

Affect, in advertisement, may be positive or negative (Watson, Clark and Tellegen, 1988). Positive affect results more in positive attitudes, tendency and intentions towards the advertised product/service while negative affects may result in more negative consumer attitude towards the advertised product/service (cf. Table 1). According to Sojka and Giese (1997), individuals may demonstrate a propensity to process information using affect or cognition, both or neither.

Table 1: Positive Affect and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS)

Affect	Attitude
POSITIVE AFFECT	Attentive, interested, alert, excited, enthusiastic, inspired, proud, determined, strong, active
NEGATIVE AFFECT	Distressed, disinterest, upset, hostile, irritable, scared, afraid, ashamed, guilty, nervous, jittery

Source: Watson, Clark and Tellegen 1988

Cognition has been linked to affect in several studies (Zajonc and Markus, 1982; Burke and Edell, 1989; Halimahtun, 2006). Affect has been linked to realism, recall and involvement (Frijda, 1988; Gollnisch and Averill, 1993; Grabe, 2000; Grodal, 2009; Rooney, Benson and Hannessy, 2012) although caution is expressed about assumptions of causation. Involvement can be in the forms of attention, interest, desire, cognition or emotions, which influence action, or, as relating to this study, behavioural preferences upon exposure to advertising stimuli. This informed the adoption of a modified AIDA model, for the purpose of this study, which assessed the effectiveness of the respondents' preferred television advertisements based on attention, interest/desire and action in relation to recall and communication effectiveness.

Considering the disparity in the responses of individuals to advertisements, this study therefore adopted a relatively holistic approach in assessing the impact of CGI on advertisement effectiveness by surveying the respondents' opinions based only on their individual choices or preferred television advertisements.

2.2. Computer Generated Imagery in Television Advertisements

CGI-embedded adverts are simply adverts with (significant) level or quantity of computer generated imagery integrated into them. Majority of the new generation television adverts are embedded with CGI, even though not all effective adverts out in the market today are necessarily CGI-embedded. There have been some non-CGI-embedded TV adverts that have fared well in the market: examples include the Indomie "Mama you do good" and the Guinness "Rivalry" adverts which were almost totally void of CGI.

According to Danny (2010), the beauty of CGI technology is its flexibility. Danny further asserts that computer generated assets can turn a casual interest in a product into sales and make

a serious difference to a company's bottom line. Examples of ways or techniques through which CGI-technology has been integrated into television advertisement production, include:

2.2.1 2D OR 3D modelling

In advertising, 3D modelling has appeared in the forms of:

- (a)** Computer generated car models: as represented in the car-brand television adverts/promotional videos of NISSAN, BMW and TOYOTA brands (Figures 1 and 2).
- (b)** Photo-realistic computer generated models of products which are afterwards integrated into technically and carefully tailored, motion-tracked, live action footages or recordings as utilized in the Dabur Herbal toothpaste 'show me your-32' and the Indomie television adverts (Figures 3 and 4).
- (c)** Near photo-realistic human models that may even serve as stand-ins for real human models, actors or actresses, as represented in the development of the supporting female characters of the hair-care product Herbal Essence (Figure 5).
- (d)** Virtual character models such as 'Louie the fly' the ever-green popular Mortein television adverts and promotional videos character (plate 06), the Donkey in the hair-care product Herbal Essence advert (Figures 7a and 7b), or the virtual character stand-in of the main-character in the Mouka form advert (Figures 8a and 8b).

Figure 1: CGI of a Nissan car brand (in the Nissan advert)

Source: The Nissan Advert 2010

Figure 2: CGI of a BMW car brand (in the BMW advert)

Source: The BMW Advert 2010

Figure 3: CGI of the Dabur Herbal toothpaste (in a totally virtual environment)

Source: The Dabur Herbal 'Show me your 32' Advert 2008.

Figure 4: CGI of the Indomie Noodle pack.

Source: <http://www.indomie.ng> 2015

Figure 5: Computer generated models in the hair-care product, Herbal Essence's, advert (in a totally virtual environment)

Source: The Herbal Essence Advert 2008.

Figure 6: CGI of the Mortein insecticide's promotional mascot 'Louie the fly'.

source: www.dailytelegraph.com.au 2015

Figure 7a and 7b: CGI of the Donkey in the hair-care product, Herbal Essence's, advert.

Source: The Herbal Essence Advert 2008

Figure 8a: The real Mouka-form-advert's main character.

Source: The Mouka Foam Advert 2013.

Figure 8b: The computer generated stand-in for the Mouka form advert's main character.

Source: The Mouka Foam Advert 2013

2.2.2 Physical Simulations

This involves the simulation of the way bodies of many types are affected by a variety of physical stimuli. An example is the physical simulated cloud-movements as well as of the fire/tornado in the Guinness advert (Figures 9a and 9b).

Figure 9: CGI showing cloud-movement simulation in the Guinness Tornado advert.

Source: The Guinness Tornado Advert 2010

Figure 9: CGI showing fire/tornado -movement simulation in the Guinness Tornado advert.

Source: The Guinness Tornado Advert 2010

2.2.3 Motion Tracking

Motion Tracking allows the insertion of computer graphics into live-action footage with correct positioning, scaling, orientation, and motion relative to the photographed objects in a recorded footage. This technique is used for the introduction of virtual characters into live-action footages, or vice versa, as in the Chase-Freedom Credit Card advert (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Showing a live-action character walking in a 100% virtual environment in the Chase-Freedom Credit Card advert

Source: Chase-Freedom Credit Card adverts 2008.

2.3. Measuring the Effectiveness of Television Advertisements

CGI-Embedded adverts are simply adverts with (significant) level or quantity of computer generated imagery integrated into them. Majority of the new generation television adverts are embedded with CGI, even though not all effective adverts out in Over the decades, different techniques, metrics, methodology and models, ranging from non-linear to simple linear and multivariate linear models, have been used in the measurement of the effectiveness of advertisements. The Starch's model (Starch, 1923) and the Krugman non-memory dependent advertising model, (Krugman, 1977) were some of the earliest known models. However, the advertising industry has always favoured very simple hierarchical models in which advertisement effectiveness can be determined by collecting data relating to one of the intermediate stages of the model one decides to adopt. Therefore, one model that stands prominent till date is the AIDA model, a behavioural model, which was used in a slightly modified form in this research in order to assess the impact of CGI on television advertisement effectiveness.

2.3.1. The AIDA Model

The AIDA model of measuring advertising effectiveness, according to Rawal (2013), stands for **A**ttention, **I**nterest, **D**esire, and **A**ction. It is perhaps the simplest formula ever and, yet, also the most powerful (Rawal, 2013). As suggested in the AIDA model, for an advertisement to be considered effective, it has to be one that: commands **A**ttention, leads to **I**nterest in the product or service, inspires the **D**esire to own or use the product or service which eventually leads to **A**ction.

Sanayei et al (2013), opined that for an advertisement to contribute to success, it has to be designed so that the audience or customer passes through all these four phases, with all being equally important. Hence, the AIDA model implies that Advertising should inject memorable and believable messages that will trigger consumers to act in a certain favourable way (Brierley, 2002).

As a modification, interest and desire were collapsed while message-clarity and recall were introduced. Therefore, this study examined the impact of CGI on the recall-inducing and communicative effectiveness of television advertisements leveraging interactively on the respondents' individual advertisements, preferences or brand awareness, attention, interest/desire/feelings, perception of message clarity or believability and cognition.

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following hypotheses were put forward to guide this study:

Hypothesis 1:

H0: There is no significant relationship between computer generated imagery (CGI) and the communicative effectiveness of television advertisements.

Hypothesis 2:

H0: There is no significant relationship between computer generated imagery (CGI) and the recall of television advertisements.

4. RESEARCH METHOD

The study adopted the descriptive survey research method for the purpose of eliciting self-reports from the respondents. This method was chosen in order for the researcher to have the opportunity to describe systematically, the qualities, facts and characteristics of the given population

as factual and accurately as possible.

The sourced data included both primary and secondary. Data from the primary source was obtained from questionnaire. Data from the secondary source includes information from research work of other people, textbooks and journals.

The targeted population for the purpose of this study is the consumers of advertised products and audiences of television advertisements within the adult age range living Lagos state, Nigeria. The population sample was however selected using simple random sampling. The sample size of 398 respondents was considered for the study but only about 362 could be used for the study. In order to extract information from the selected sample group, a questionnaire was constructed and adopted as a suitable instrument for data collection. Frequencies, percentages, mode and mean were used in analyzing the collected data. With 3.0 as the computed mean, the decision rule was to accept any factor with a mean of 3.0 and above as positively perceived by the respondents and, hence accepted (A), while regarding any factor with a mean below 3.0 as negatively perceived and, therefore, rejected (R). Chi-square was the statistical tool adopted for the testing of the hypotheses. The decision rule was to reject H_0 if significance level (p-value) is less than alpha ($\alpha=0.05$, the predetermined significance level). A dichotomous analysis procedure, as used by Umoh and Adeyemi (1990), in which responses were collapsed into two areas- agree and disagree, was adopted for the purpose of testing the hypotheses. As a modification, the "Undecided" was also considered not to be in favour of the Likert items.

5. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

398 questionnaires were distributed to respondents in Lagos state. Brief discussions often preceded the administering of the questionnaires for the purpose of acquainting the respondents with the term CGI. Valid responses from 362 respondents were used for the purpose of testing the study hypotheses.

Table 2: AIDA Assessment of CGI-embedded (in contrast to non-CGI-embedded) Television Advertisements

Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage	Mode	Mean	Remark
ATTENTION	Strongly Agree	115	31.8	5	3.1	Accepted
	Agree	26	7.2			
	Undecided	92	25.4			
	Disagree	28	7.7			
	Strongly Disagree	101	27.9			
	Total	362	100			
INTEREST/DESIRE	Strongly Agree	125	34.5	5	3.2	Accepted
	Agree	34	9.4			
	Undecided	88	24.3			
	Disagree	18	5.0			
	Strongly Disagree	97	26.8			
	Total	362	100			
ACTION	Strongly Agree	101	27.9	5	3.1	Accepted
	Agree	38	10.5			
	Undecided	92	25.4			
	Disagree	45	12.4			

	Strongly Disagree	86	23.8			
	Total	362	100			

Decision: Accept a variable as positively perceived if mean is greater than the computed mean 3.0.

From the above Table 2, respondents widely agreed, with all obtained means greater than 3.0, that CGI-embedded television advertisements were more effective than non-CGI-embedded television advertisements in terms of attention, arousal of interest/desire and preferential motivation. Although caution is expressed about assumptions of causation, this can be said to have stemmed from affective, cognitive or affective-cognitive involvement in their preferred television advertisements which is not unrelated to CGI-induced message clarity as well as the measure of the advert-content that the audience could remember.

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between CGI and the communicative effectiveness of television advertisements.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between CGI and the communicative effectiveness of television advertisements.

Consumers were made to rate Non-CGI-Embedded –Advertisements against CGI-Embedded – television advertisements with message clarity as a criteria for the communication test.

Table 3: Relationship between CGI and the communicative effectiveness of television advertisements.

Variable	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
CGI-Embedded Advertisements	220	181	39
Non-CGI-Embedded Advertisements	142	181	-39
Total	362		

N	DF	Chi-Square	Significant	Decision
362	1	16.807	0.000041	Reject H ₀

Rejected at p<0.05

Since the p-value obtained is 0.000041 which is less than the predetermined significance level, the result is significant at p<0.05. Therefore, we fail to accept the null hypothesis and, hence, the alternative hypothesis, which establishes a significant relationship between CGI and the communicative effectiveness of television advertisements, is thereby accepted. This agrees with the result computed in Table 3.

Hypothesis 2:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between CGI and the recall of television advertisements.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between CGI and the recall of television advertisements.

Consumers were made to rate non-CGI-embedded –advertisements against CGI-Embedded –

television advertisements with the level of recall of the content of the TV-adverts to which they have been exposed.

Table 4: Relationship between CGI and the consumers’ recall of the content of the television advertisements to which they have been exposed

Variable	Observed N	Expected N	Residual
CGI-Embedded Advertisements	200	181	19
Non-CGI-Embedded Advertisements	162	181	-19
Total	362		

N	DF	Chi-Square	Significant	Decision
362	1	3.989	0.045798	Reject H ₀

Rejected at p<0.05

Since the p-value obtained is 0.045798 which is less than the predetermined significance level, the result is significant at p<0.05. Therefore, we fail to accept the null hypothesis and, hence, the alternative hypothesis, which establishes a significant relationship between CGI and the effectiveness of television advertisements in terms of the consumers’ recall of the content of the television advertisements to which they have been exposed, is thereby accepted. This agrees with the result computed in Table 4.

6. CONCLUSION

The study revealed that CGI is vital to advertising effectiveness in terms of communication or message clarity and as well as in aiding recall of advert-contents. The study considers this effect to stem from its influence on the attention of the consumers, cognition and affect, augmenting audiences arousal levels and, hence, influencing favourably their behavioural preferences, which often translates into wider advertising reach, improved product sales and market shares which are the major reasons for being in business in the first place.

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BIOGRAPHY

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